

Review on the Gamma Function and Error Correction

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Abstract: This paper presents a newly extended gamma function for positive real number $x \geq 1$ and correct the error in the existing gamma function. The newly extended gamma function is a special function to compute the factorial for positive real values by the integral.

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1. Introduction

The gamma function is a generalization of factorial function for positive real values and it provides error in calculation [1-3] of factorial for positive real values. In this article, newly extended gamma function is proved and it corrects error in the existing gamma function [4-6].

2. Error Correction

The existing gamma function calculates the value for $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ as follows:

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi} \approx 1.77245385091.$$

$$\Gamma(3) > \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) > \Gamma(2) \Rightarrow 2! > \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! > 1!, \text{ which is a contradiction.}$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \left(\frac{3}{2} - 1\right) \left(\frac{3}{2} - 1 - 1\right)! = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)! = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}.$$

So, $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ is not true and also calculating the value of $\Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)$ using $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ can not be true.

From these results, it is concluded that the calculated values using $\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)$ are not true.

The newly extend gamma function is

$$\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}(h) = \int_0^{\infty} x^{1-h} e^{-x} dx, h \geq 1.$$

$$\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}(1) = \int_0^{\infty} x^{1-1} e^{-x} dx = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} dx = [-e^{-x}]_0^{\infty} = 1.$$

$$\text{Here, } \Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}(h) = (h)(h-1) \cdots (3)(2)(1)! = (h)(h-1) \cdots (3)(2)\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}(1).$$

Let us calculate $\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)$ as follows:

$$\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \int_0^{\infty} x^{1-\frac{3}{2}} e^{-x} dx = \int_0^{\infty} x^{-\frac{1}{2}} e^{-x} dx$$

$$\text{Let } t = x^{\frac{1}{2}} \Rightarrow 2dt = x^{-\frac{1}{2}} dx$$

$$\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t^2} dt = 2 \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-t^2} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t^2} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2 \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-t^2} dt \int_0^{\infty} e^{-s^2} ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\text{Let } t = sz \Rightarrow dt = sdz$$

$$\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = 2 \left(\int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t^2-s^2} dt ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2 \left(\int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-s^2z^2-s^2} sdz ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2 \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-(1+z^2)s^2} sdz ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$= 2 \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-(1+z^2)s^2} sdz ds \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2 \left(\int_0^{\infty} \left[-\frac{1}{2(1+z^2)} e^{-(1+z^2)s^2} \right]_0^{\infty} dz \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$= 2 \left(\int_0^{\infty} \left[0 + \frac{1}{2(1+z^2)} \right] dz \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1+z^2)} dz \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = 2^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1+z^2)} dz \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2^{\frac{1}{2}} ([\tan^{-1}(z)]_0^{\infty})^{\frac{1}{2}} = 2^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - 0 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \sqrt{\pi}.$$

$$\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi} \approx 1.77245385091.$$

$$\Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}\left(\frac{5}{2}\right) = \left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \left(\frac{5}{2} - 1\right)! = \left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)! = \left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \Gamma_{\mathbb{R}}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \sqrt{\pi}.$$

Thus, the newly extended gamma function approximates the positive real value, which is greater than or equal to 1.

3. Conclusion

In this article, a newly extended gamma function has been introduced to approximate the right values.

References

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